

REVIGORAREA METODELOR DE PREDARE A DREPTULUI ÎN ERA DIGITALĂ

Reinvigorationg law teaching methods in the digital age

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Summary. Currently, teaching law means teaching students traditional reasoning, but also helping them to build, to invent reasoning. Legal education is the channel through which methodological and epistemological concerns flow. Among the tools that generate legal solutions, logic and legal concepts are usually the preferred ones. However, the concepts are perceived not as simple definitions, but as a comprehensive systematization of the legal matter. The development of artificial intelligence seems to put pressure on the ability of human intelligence to provide the best legal solutions, to make the best choices, generalizations, conclusions. In such circumstances, the representatives of legal professions and, in particular, of university legal education, feel the need to make additional efforts, in order to adapt, through resilience, to new realities and to preserve, to the same extent, the foundations of logical thinking in the digital age. The paper is developed in the context of realization of the ‘Strengthening socio-economic and legal mechanisms to ensure the well-being and security of the citizens’ Project (CONSEJ 01.05.02).

Key words: didactic process, legal professions, methodology, artificial intelligence, human intelligence.

Introduction

How should law be taught at the contemporary stage so that the teaching-learning-evaluating process is adapted to the demands of the digital age? What are the dilemmas facing academia? To what extent does the development of artificial intelligence (AI) influence this process? And how do we adapt to these changes? There are several questions that we try to find answers to in this research.

Purpose and objectives of the study. The purpose of the study is to argue the need to adapt the legal academic environment to the new trends of social development, including in the digital sphere, by revitalizing the methods of teaching law, diversified according to the subject of the course, addressees, curricular objectives and expected learning outcomes.

In order to achieve the purpose, several research objectives are proposed: 1) synthesizing the specifics of the traditional methods of teaching law at the contemporary stage; 2)

evaluation of the dilemmas faced by the university community in the process of teaching-learning-evaluation of law, through the lens of the effectiveness of teaching methods; 3) setting up benchmarks for adapting the methods of teaching law to social development trends, including in the digital area.

Research hypotheses. In developing the study, we start from two research hypotheses.

Firstly, the unprecedented development of information technologies and the massive digitization of processes dictates the indispensability of making qualitative changes in the traditional way of viewing the world of law and training legal professionals capable of adapting to new realities. An academic community neglecting the impact of the digital age on the nature of the skills of legal professionals (and, respectively, future legal professionals) may negatively affect the quality of university legal studies and the degree of integration of graduates into the labour market.

Secondly, limiting the process of teaching law to the tools offered by information technologies, including the use of AI, could negatively affect the level of training of legal professionals, from the point of view of the ability to analyse, interpret, argue, develop solutions through the power of human intelligence. Such skills are able to increase the resilience of jurists in conditions of permanent change and the ability to discern between truthful and untruthful, rational and irrational, current and obsolete. To the same extent, the encouragement of thinking, as a natural process of the evolution of civilization, places the legal professional in the contextual area of human existence, interpreting laws and making individualized decisions regarding human destinies.

Therefore, the mission of law schools today should be based on the multidimensional training of future lawyers, through the balanced approach of traditional and innovative methodologies of teaching-learning-evaluation of law. We opt for a revival of law teaching methods, by adapting to contexts and realities, with the acceptance of AI as a facilitator of this process and not as a substitute for human intelligence. However, in their daily activity, legal professionals have a direct connection with the area of human rights, their legitimate interests, social welfare and citizens' security; and the individual needs human treatment, through operations of human intelligence, including at the level of emotional intelligence. The digital age should be perceived as a field of possibilities for automating processes, assisting human activity and thus improving legal professions.

Achievement of objectives.

How is law taught at universities?

Currently, the curricula at law faculties are developed based on objectives and learning outcomes adapted to the requirements of the labour market. Teachers have the freedom to select the appropriate teaching methods, so that they correspond to the curricular milestones and contribute to the formation and consolidation of skills necessary for integration in a distinct professional area. There is no hierarchy of teaching methodologies. Each discipline has its own specifics and teaching-learning-assessment methods vary according to these specifics.

Law is an objective historical reality, an expanding measure of freedom and justice in the life of society¹, whose usefulness results from the need for the general reconciliation

¹ Ion Guceac, Dreptul în mecanismul de reglementare a relațiilor sociale [Law in the mechanism of regulation of social relations], in: Criza dreptului între aspirații democratice și repere axiologice [in]existente [The crisis of law between democratic aspirations and [non-]existent axiological bench-

of the requirements, values and representations of each of the other spheres (economic, sanitary, religious, technological, etc.)² Law encompasses a vast and complex field, both from the perspective of the theoretical-applicative substance, and from the perspective of alignment with a wide spectrum of professional profiles. In the event of the proliferation of tensions between political factors and the professional environment, the imperious nature of the need for the right to remain faithful to its social mission and to find itself as a constant quality of actions is imposed³. For these reasons, the teaching of law is focused on the development of logical thinking, critical thinking, which determines the valorisation of some methods of teaching law that contribute to the formation and consolidation of this kind of skills in students, future lawyers. In this sense, traditional methods are often used, such as: *the lecture*, as a classic method for theoretical courses, intended for a large number of students, coming from several academic groups; *the Socratic method*, based on a dialogue between the teacher and the students, in which challenging questions are launched, so that the students arrive, in a guided manner, at certain logical answers; *brainstorming* or *brainwriting*, as a variety of the first method, which proves its usefulness in enlivening the audience and launching a multitude of ideas, which can later be systematized, exemplified, analysed, assessed; *the case study*, which allows the application of normative-legal regulations to a concrete case, usually taken from reality and adapted according to the study cycle (bachelor's degree, master's degree); *problematization*, which has been trending in recent years, because it stimulates creativity and inventiveness in solving current problems for the legal sphere; *the project method*, included as mandatory in the II cycle, master, to encourage work in interdisciplinary teams, with the aim of identifying a concrete issue in the legal professional environment and designing viable solutions to prevent and overcome it, through consistent steps and concrete mechanisms, etc. Many other methods and techniques are used at different phases of the didactic act, with greater or lesser frequency (Venn diagram, guided discussion, panel discussion, etc.), of great importance being to achieve continuity between cycles of higher education by capitalizing on didactic methods⁴.

Starting from the specifics of law as a science and discipline, the teaching methods also have certain particularities. If, for example, an audience were to learn how to build a fence, surely several methods of learning could be used: reading the rules in a textbook; listening to a lecture about these rules; viewing consecutive images or a video that reflects the process; watching a fence being built online in real time; direct participation in building the fence. Each of these methods could be useful. It is certain, however, that those who will directly participate in the construction of the fence, accompanied by relevant theoretical

marks], Chisinau: Cartea Juridica, Lexon Prim, 2023, pp. 22.

² François Ost, cited by Dierickx Gauthier, Fr. Ost. Nouveaux contes juridiques, Paris, Dalloz, 2021, 200 p, in: *Révue interdisciplinaire d'études juridiques*; 2022/1, vol.88, pp. 253-258. DOI 10.3917/riej.088.0253. [online] <https://www.cairn.info/revue-interdisciplinaire-d-etudes-juridiques-2022-1-page-253.html#pa6> (consulted 15.08.2024).

³ Rodica Ciobanu. Integritatea - rațiunea de „a fi” și necesitate de modernizare [Integrity – the reason ,to be’ and the need for modernisation], in: *Studia Universitatis Moldaviae (Seria Științe Sociale)*, 2023, n. 8(168), pp. 55. [online] DOI: [https://doi.org/10.59295/sum8\(168\)2023_08](https://doi.org/10.59295/sum8(168)2023_08) (consulted 15.08.2024).

⁴ Vladimir Guțu, Metodele didactice – mijloc de realizare a continuității și interacțiunii între cicluri de învățământ superior [Teaching methods - means of achieving continuity and interaction between higher education cycles], in: *Studia Universitatis Moldaviae*, 2019, n. 9(129), pp. 62. [online] https://ibn.idsi.md/sites/default/files/imag_file/09.%20p.57-62.pdf (consulted 15.08.2024).

explanations, will benefit from the most effective methodology: in this case, the teaching method seems to be in direct accordance with the objective and the learning outcome.

A similar approach is needed in relation to the design of law courses. For these reasons, the teaching of law is also done through the interpretation of concrete legal norms; analysis of international and national jurisprudence; presenting arguments; drafting legal acts (petitions, requests, references, court decisions, summaries of court decisions).

Interactive methods, which combine learning, in the sense of knowledge accumulation, with the development of other level skills (analysis, application, evaluation, argumentation, design, forecasting), including the skills conventionally accepted under the name of soft skills (communication, teamwork, adaptability, managing conflicts, emotions, etc.) enjoy increased attractiveness. In this sense, activities such as legal clinics, moot court competitions; debates on certain legal issues; memo writing contests and pleading contests gain ascendancy.

A substantial role in strengthening practical skills is attributed to practical trainings, by specialty. Basically, opportunities to be initiated in a legal career are highly valued by law schools globally (we mean internships and externships); however, the way they are organized and carried out is conceptually different in each jurisdiction; at the present time there is a need to (re-)think such opportunities, institutionalized, for future law professionals at the national level.

What dilemmas does the university community face in the process of teaching-learning-evaluation of law, in terms of the effectiveness of teaching methods?

The digital age has offered both advantages and disadvantages, including risks, which led the academic environment to change their vision of the teaching process and adapt to new realities. ‘Failing to recognize changes in students, from one generation to the other (particularly changes in the way they process information) represents a major part of the problem in legal education’⁵. The advantages of advanced technologies are known and accepted by the society. Access to the internet basically equates to unlimited access to information, social and professional communication networks, online work, digitization of processes, etc.

On the other hand, in the educational process AI is increasingly exploited by students in carrying out teaching tasks. At the moment, the chatbot has become quite popular, thanks to its ability to do complex legal analysis, exemplification, synthesis, restructuring and even drafting legal content. Law students also use conversational interfaces to give answers to assessment tests, to write legal arguments, to summarize generalized interpretations of jurisprudence, to give legal solutions, to create contents, etc. In such circumstances, the teacher is practically forced by the situation to rethink both teaching and evaluation methods, so that the university's mission regarding the training of professionals for the labour market in the legal field is achieved.

The use of AI generates dilemmas for the entire academic environment. On the one hand, teachers must assimilate the opportunities that cutting-edge technologies can offer to the teaching process. Teaching methodologies could be supplemented with methods involving the direct use of computers and AI to increase the attractiveness of the process from the student's perspective. On the other hand, ‘the technology seems incapable to solve real-world

⁵ Benjamin V. Madison, The Elephant in law school classrooms: overuse of the Socratic method as an obstacle to teaching modern law students, in: *University of Detroit Mercy Law Review*, 2008, vol.85:293, pp. 295. [online] <https://www.ialsnet.org/wp-content/uploads/2015/10/Benjamin-Madison.pdf> (consulted 15.08.2024).

problems’, requiring both a technical and a humanistic approach, or through the prism of a ‘technical aesthetics of law’⁶. Practice proves that the use of AI still requires a certain training, knowledge of certain rules. The information compiled or analysed by a chatbot may not be truthful. It needs to be checked. Frequently enough, using the chatbot to complete academic tasks, students provided erroneous data as an answer. In such circumstances, the role of the teacher is crucial. The errors are explained to the student, to make him or her understand the risks to which he or she can be exposed when abandoning the logical approach to the legal issue, by using the power of thinking. And, if in the didactic process the error may not be a substantial or decisive one, in the legal area practice the error may be fatal.

In other legal systems there are high-profile cases where lawyers have faced serious problems as a result of using ChatGPT. In Canada, in 2023, a lawyer was investigated in connection with the presentation in court of documents, citing solutions offered by ChatGPT, developed by Open AI. More precisely, in a case of child custody, she referred to some non-existent jurisprudence cases, a fact which was objected to by the opposing party’s lawyer⁷. Similarly, in the U.S. there were situations when the lawyers invoked in the documents presented to the court, in support of their position, non-existent jurisprudence cases. Some of them were fined (including the law firm of which the lawyers were part)⁸, others were referred to disciplinary boards for appropriate investigations⁹ or even suspended from office for a certain period of time¹⁰. In the United States the increasing use of ChatGPT by lawyers for drafting legal acts has led some judges to issue ‘a certification requirement about artificial intelligence that all attorneys must complete’, referring to the fact that the document presented to the court does not contain fragments of text created by AI or that would not have been verified by a human being.¹¹

It is useful to discuss these things with students, even within the course hours, by analysing the risks of providing, when solving a legal issue, untrue data, created by LLMs (Large Language Models). Also, to support the young generation’s major temptation towards new technologies, they can be involved in the teaching methodology. Essential aspects for the area of law, connected to digital processes, are also the issues of securing

⁶ Annelise Riles, A New Agenda for the Cultural Study of Law: Taking on the Technicalities, in: Cornell Law Faculty Publications, 2005, paper 782, pp. 976, 977. [online] <http://scholarship.law.cornell.edu/facpub/782> (consulted 15.08.2024).

⁷ Canada lawyer under fier for submitting fake cases created by AI chatbot. Ching Ke, from Vancouver, under investigation after allegedly using ChatGPT to cite case law – bu those did not exist, in: The Guardian, 29 February 2024. [online] <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2024/feb/29/canada-lawyer-chatgpt-fake-cases-ai> (consulted 15.08.2024).

⁸ The two lawyers fined for submitting fake court citations from ChatGPT. Law firm also penalised after chatbot invented six legal cases that were then used in an aviation injury claim, in: The Guardian, 23 June 2023. [online] <https://www.theguardian.com/technology/2023/jun/23/two-us-lawyers-fined-submitting-fake-court-citations-chatgpt> (consulted 15.08.2024).

⁹ Park v. Kim, 22-2057, United States Court of Appeals for the Second Circuit, August term 2023. [online] <https://fingfx.thomsonreuters.com/gfx/legaldocs/egvbaanybqp/2nd%20Circuit%20Decision.pdf> (consulted 15.08.2024).

¹⁰ Colorado Atty suspended for using ‘sham’ ChatGPT case law. Defender Services Office. Training Division. 28 November 2023. [online] <https://www.fd.org/news/colorado-atty-suspended-using-sham-chatgpt-case-law> (consulted 15.08.2024).

¹¹ Joseph Anderson, AI and the legal puzzle: filling gaps, but missing pieces, in: Mercer Law Review, 2024, vol.75, no.5 Companion Edition, art.8, pp. 1543-1544. [online] https://digitalcommons.law.mercer.edu/jour_mlr/vol75/iss5/8 (consulted 15.08.2024).

data, protecting private life, ethical communication, etc. ‘[G]enerative AI models may [...] make mistakes in citation, not understand the distinction between precedential and binding authority [...]’¹². Ultimately, regardless of the method selected to create legal content, build legal arguments, make legal decisions, the responsibility for the accuracy of the substance rests with the author - the human being. So, ‘[i]f AI tools are used, AI should be used to complement human judgment’¹³.

What would be the benchmarks for adapting the methods of teaching law to social development trends, including in the digital area?

Law teaching methods are to be adapted to digital innovations gradually, consistently and stably, the multiple advantages of these innovations being difficult to dispute. However, it is necessary to be guided by certain guidelines, of an ethical and legal nature, so that the use of AI does not generate critical consequences for people. It is unrealistic to prohibit the use of AI tools by law students and legal professionals. ‘Law schools should prioritize allowing law students access to AI tools and the ability to practice using them in a guided classroom setting [...], should create clear guidelines and update their university policies to include permitted and prohibited uses of generative AI for both staff and students’¹⁴.

It is imperative to establish some rules, principles for using the data created in this way. The information provided by the AI must be verified, subjected to an exercise of additional analysis, through the prism of the knowledge ordinarily accumulated in the study process. The sources to which the LLM refers, for instance, must be verified; or, in the case of presenting a product of legal writing, either official or of a doctrinal nature, it is necessary to refer to the original, truthful source, both for reasons of legality, soundness, and ethics. For example, if reference is made to a legal norm, to jurisprudence, the risk that these are non-existent or inapplicable to the case, or misinterpreted, may irreparably affect the solution proposed by the jurist and, consequently, his career or the fate of the litigant concerned. Similarly, a lawyer invoking a normative-legal regulation, or a case of non-existent jurisprudence can be assessed as having bad faith conduct. An author of a scientific paper making inappropriate use of AI can be accused of plagiarism.

In doctrine, although not in the format of unique and unanimously accepted definitions, there is the term of *hallucinations* to denote erroneous information or non-existent data about certain phenomena, events, provided by AI as if they could be real. ‘[H]allucination refers to instances where non-existent objects are erroneously detected or incorrectly localized at their anticipated positions’¹⁵. And ‘challenges presented by legal hallucinations are not only

¹² S. Sean Tu, Amy Cyphert & Samuel J. Perl, Artificial Intelligence: Legal Reasoning, Legal Research and Legal Writing, in: Minnesota Journal of Law, Science & Technology, 2024, vol.25, issue 2, art.11, pp. 112. [online] <https://scholarship.law.umn.edu/mjlst/vol25/iss2/11> (consulted 15.08.2024).

¹³ Hon. Xavier Rodriguez, Artificial Intelligence (AI) and the practice of law, in: The Sedona Conference Journal, forthcoming 2023, vol.24, 783, pp. 817. [online] <https://texasbarsections.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/11/Rodriguez-Paper.pdf> (consulted 15.08.2024).

¹⁴ Hon. Xavier Rodriguez, Artificial Intelligence (AI) and the practice of law, in: The Sedona Conference Journal, forthcoming 2023, vol.24, 783, pp. 821. [online] <https://texasbarsections.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/11/Rodriguez-Paper.pdf> (consulted 15.08.2024).

¹⁵ Negar Maleki, Balaji Padmanabhan, Dutta Kaushik, AI hallucinations: a misnomer worth clarifying, in: 2024 IEEE Conference on Artificial Intelligence (CAI), Singapore, 2024, pp.133. [online] doi: 10.1109/CAI59869.2024.00033 (consulted 15.08.2024).

empirical, but also normative¹⁶. Adapting the contemporary methods of teaching law to the innovations of information technologies also means learning how to detect and treat these hallucinations in the legal sphere. Filtering data through the human mind remains the most reliable mechanism for creating and interpreting data and making decisions in legal matters. ‘AI tools for legal research have not eliminated hallucinations. Users of these tools must continue to verify that key propositions are accurately supported by citations’¹⁷. ‘Critically, no lawyer should submit autonomously generated product to a court without first checking the accuracy of the product and that the attorney is not violating any local rules in using artificial intelligence’¹⁸. In such circumstances, the total abandonment of traditional and modern methods of teaching law would make the act of learning law and the act of justice itself vulnerable and arbitrary. Replacing human intelligence with AI ‘may bring a culture of incompetence’¹⁹. ‘Lawyers play an important role in helping ensure that law evolves and develops in ways that benefit and mirror society’ and the overuse of LLM ‘could cause stagnation in the development of law’²⁰. ‘AI cannot be creative because it necessarily relies on the information that was fed into its algorithm. Overreliance on AI for creating legal arguments could result in a legal framework that fails to adapt to changing societal values. Instead, the law might become entrenched in the societal snapshot present at the time of the algorithm’s creation’²¹.

On the other hand, the researcher can propose a new interpretation of a known subject or an original interpretation of an unknown, new subject, by integrating in the scientific approach not only the practice of law, but also social experience²²; law cannot be confused with laws and judicial practice, although it is directly related to them²³. The scientific approach of the researcher - human being - is also correlated with a certain level of legal

¹⁶ Matthew Dahl, Varun Magesh, Mirac Suzgun, Daniel E. Ho, Large legal fictions: profiling legal hallucinations in large language models, in: *Journal of Legal Analysis* (forthcoming), pp. 36. [online] <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2401.01301>. <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2401.01301> (consulted 15.08.2024).

¹⁷ Varun Magesh, Faiz Surani, Matthew Dahl, Mirac Suzgun, Christopher D. Manning, Daniel E. Ho, Hallucination-free? Assessing the reliability of leading AI research tools, pp. 23. [online] <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2405.20362><https://arxiv.org/abs/2405.20362> (consulted 15.08.2024)

¹⁸ Joseph Anderson, AI and the legal puzzle: filling gaps, but missing pieces, in: *Mercer Law Review*, 2024, vol.75, no.5 Companion Edition, art.8, pp. 1542. [online] https://digitalcommons.law.mercer.edu/jour_mlr/vol75/iss5/8 (consulted 15.08.2024).

¹⁹ Joseph Anderson, AI and the legal puzzle: filling gaps, but missing pieces, in: *Mercer Law Review*, 2024, vol.75, no.5 Companion Edition, art.8, pp. 1552. [online] https://digitalcommons.law.mercer.edu/jour_mlr/vol75/iss5/8 (consulted 15.08.2024).

²⁰ Amy Cyphert, Samuel J. Perl, Sean JD Tu S., AI cannibalism and the law, in: *Colorado Technology Law Journal*, 2024, vol.22.2, 301, pp. 316. [online] https://ctlj.colorado.edu/wp-content/uploads/2024/07/FINAL_05.25.24_CPT_AI-Cannibalism-and-the-Law.pdf (consulted 15.08.2024).

²¹ S. Sean Tu, Amy Cyphert & Samuel J. Perl, Artificial Intelligence: legal reasoning, legal research and legal writing, in: *Minnesota Journal of Law, Science & Technology*, 2024, vol.25, issue 2, art.11, pp. 121. [online] <https://scholarship.law.umn.edu/mjlst/vol25/iss2/11> (consulted 15.08.2024).

²² Elena Aramă, Unele reflecții metodologice despre cercetarea juridică la etapa doctoratului, in: *Studia Universitatis Moldaviae (Seria Științe Sociale)*, 2023, n. 3(163), pp. 18. [online] DOI: [https://doi.org/10.59295/sum3\(163\)2023_02](https://doi.org/10.59295/sum3(163)2023_02) (consulted 15.08.2024).

²³ Elena Arama, O privire retrospectivă asupra crizei dreptului [A retrospective look at the crisis of law,], in: *Criza dreptului între aspirații democratice și repere axiologice [in]existente [The crisis of law between democratic aspirations and [non-]existent axiological benchmarks]*, Chisinau: Cartea Juridică, Lexon Prim, 2023, pp. 84.

culture, which is intrinsic to the process of individual and social development and is based equally on *knowledge* and *behaviour*²⁴, as inseparable defining dimensions. In the same way, interdisciplinarity is an indispensable way for approaching law. For instance, Annelise Riles emphasizes the close connection between law and anthropology; starting from this postulate, Lucy Welsh concludes that ‘[p]ure legal process has the potential to reduce multi-layered issues to single conclusion, and could mean that important aspects of particular problems are relegated to the past without ever being fully addressed’²⁵. But AI, in any context, should be ‘human-centered’²⁶.

Conclusions. Following the analysis of the subject proposed for examination, we can conclude that the didactic, scientific and ethical area of the process of teaching legal subjects in the university setting is currently at the intersection of the great problems of humanity, including human rights, dignity, as well as solidarity in relationships between people, but also in relationships between the individual and the society in the age of digital technologies. Are current teaching methods able to advance or not to the benefit of preserving the main results of the evolution of human civilization?

The epistemological aspect of the teaching-learning process is greatly facilitated with the implementation of new technological resources, which can serve as a starting point, but not as a final result of university studies in law. Much more serious problems are posed to this process by the slightly frivolous attitude of some people as unconscious consumers of technological products. Students should be warned about this tendency, who, due to their young age, may be inclined to follow less orthodox paths in their career. Emphasis must be placed on the independent, critical thinking of students, which will develop their innovative and creative spirit.

Our academic community faces new challenges, to which it must respond, therefore the initiation of methodological discussions on these topics can be of real benefit to both teachers and students, given the common expectations related to the future of legal professions, the role of preserving the best traditional methods of teaching legal subjects, combined with procedures, techniques made available by AI. But the major warning for future professionals must be inserted in the deontological, ethical framework of the profession of law, so that the lawyer is only helped by the new technologies, but not subordinated to them, because in that unfortunate case (of subordination) he or she can lose control not only over his or her career, but also on his or her own life and the lives of other people.

The paper is developed in the context of realization of the „Strengthening socio-economic and legal mechanisms to ensure the well-being and security of the citizens” Project (CONSEJ 01.05.02).

²⁴ Rodica Ciobanu, Cultura juridică [ne] ajunsă la maturitate. O necesitate de revalorizare? [The legal culture (non)reaching maturity. A need for reevaluation?] in: 100 de ani de la adoptarea constituției României de la 1923. Evoluții context și perspective europene în România și Republica Moldova [100 years since the adoption of the Romanian constitution of 1923. Contextual developments and European perspectives in Romania and the Republic of Moldova], 24 March 2023, Chisinau: CEP USM, 2023, pp. 45. [online] DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8412697> (consulted 15.08.2024).

²⁵ Lucy Welsh, The role of law in temporal reasoning: an interview of Annelise Riles, in: *Feminist Legal Studies*, 2017, 25, pp. 129. [online] <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10691-017-9340-5> (consulted 15.08.2024).

²⁶ Matthew Dahl, Varun Magesh, Mirac Suzgun, Daniel E. Ho, Large legal fictions: profiling legal hallucinations in large language models, in: *Journal of Legal Analysis*, (forthcoming), pp. 37. [online] <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2401.01301>. <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2401.01301> (consulted 15.08.2024).